

AUTHORITY

Title : British National Bibliography

Publisher : The British Library

Place of Publication : United Kingdom (Britain)

First Edition : 1950

INTRODUCTION

The British National Bibliography (BNB) is the national bibliography of the United Kingdom. It lists the books, serials and electronic publications that are newly published or distributed in the United Kingdom and Republic of Ireland that are received by the British Library under legal deposit. It started to maintain the print publication records since 1950 and the electronic publications since 2003. UK and Irish publishers are obliged by law to send a copy of all new publications including the serial titles to BNB for listing. It also contains details of the forthcoming publications. The BNB Online is updated daily as well as the PDF of new titles is available weekly.

HISTORY

- It was established in 1949 in response to the recommendations of Lionel McColvin (librarian) who had undertaken a survey of the public library service in 1942 which resulted in the McColvin Report.
- He found that the library tended to consist of very brief entries which contained little description and they did not provide the user with information on books not held by that library.
- He identified a need for a weekly list of full catalogue records of new books which could also be used by libraries to create their catalogues.

- The Council of the British National Bibliography was established in March 1949. The new national bibliography commenced full operations in 1950 and consisted of weekly lists of all books and first issues of new serial titles published in Great Britain.
- Each title was catalogued in accordance with the Anglo-American Code and classified according to the Dewey Decimal Classification system.
- Author/title indexes were provided every four weeks and the lists were collected together and produced into an annual volume.

SCOPE

- The BNB aims to publish an accurate and comprehensive bibliographical records of new publications in U.K. and Republic of Ireland.
- Media covered by BNB are books, serial as well as the electronic publications.
- It contains over 4.5 million records (as of Sept. 2019) on all subjects since 1950 to till date.
- The BNB is created in partnership with the five other British libraries and Irish libraries allowing the privilege of legal deposit, under the Legal Deposit Libraries Shared Cataloguing Programme (LDLSCP). The five libraries along with the British library are the Bodleian library (Oxford), Cambridge University library, the National Library of Scotland, The National Library of Wales and the Library of Trinity College Dublin.
- The Legal Deposit Libraries Shared Cataloguing Programme (LDLSCP) is a programme based on an agreement between the six legal deposit libraries of the United Kingdom and Ireland to share responsibility for cataloguing the legal deposit intake of

new publications aiming to maximise the quality and coverage of the BNB.

- The British Library coordinates the UK Cataloguing-in-Publication (CIP) Programme and includes CIP records in the BNB which provides records of new and forthcoming books in advance of publication in the United Kingdom and Ireland, which are included in the BNB. Information on new titles appears up to 16 weeks ahead of the announced publication date. Advance information on well over 50,000 titles each year is provided in this way.
- There are some publications which are not recorded in BNB, this is because they are more properly recorded elsewhere. Some of them are:
 - Publications without a British or Irish imprint and without a UK distributor.
 - Certain official publications such as Parliamentary & Non-parliamentary papers such as publications of an administrative nature, reports on individual institutions such as schools, factories, prisons, police forces etc.
 - Electoral rolls, Telephone directories, Publicity material e.g. advertisements, publications giving information for local residents, visitors, commercial firms etc.
 - Music scores, maps, CDs containing films or television programmes.
 - Computer software, apps.
 - Patents and calendars.

TREATMENT

Enough information within the records is given to enable a user to

make a decision on whether to obtain the item but full details for a title may be found by searching the BNB online.

The following information is given for each publication:

- Dewey class number
- Title and statement of responsibility
- Publication details
- Physical description
- Language
- Terms of Availability
- ISBN Number
- BNB Number
- Library of Congress of Subject Headings

ARRANGEMENT

BNB is arranged in classified order.

Each entry in the classified part contains the usual bibliographic details as per the rules of AACR-2 including the price, ISBN as well as BNB serial number.

BNB produce a weekly list of new records as a PDF arranged according to 20th edition of Dewey classification and are catalogued according to 2nd edition of AACR.

FORMAT

- It is available in print as well as in an online format.

- The BNB online is updated daily.
- The PDF of new titles are available weekly.
- The last printed weekly list appeared in December 2011.
- The British National Bibliography continues to exist as an online service at <http://bnb.bl.uk>.

The list is now produced in two formats:

- As a PDF arranged in Dewey classification number order.
- In RDF/XML for those who need a format which can be manipulated by computer.

RDF is Resource Description Framework which is a framework for describing resources on the web. (XML) Extensible Markup Language is used to describe data in a flexible way to create information formats and electronically share data via the public Internet.

- All of BNB is available for searching on Z39.50 service which allows downloading records in MARC21 for free.

KEY FEATURES OF ONLINE FORMAT

1. All of BNB is available for searching at <http://bnb.bl.uk>.
2. Advanced search option is available.
3. Provides information about BNB collection metadata.
4. Guide the user about the usage of BNB online as by helping them to know about:
 - Browser requirement.
 - Log In :- No need to log in to search the catalogue. It need
Log in only if there is a Reader or Customer of On Demand Document Supply Service.

- Change Password or edit account details.
- Provides Search Tips :-

How to enter search terms.

How to search people's name.

Search for items published in a specific year.

Search for newspaper editions.

- Managing the Results :-

Refine:- We may not see the record we want because the search finds lots of results. We can Refine the results to reduce the number of records. There are a number of Refine options available.

Sorting:- According to Date-newest or oldest, title, author.

- How to print, save or e-mail records.
- How to save searches.
- Using My Workspace.
- How to Order or View items.

5. Free data service named Z39.50 allows downloading records in MARC21 for free.

6. All of BNB is available in basic RDF/XML. Details are at <http://www.bl.uk/bibliographic/datafree.html>

7. New records are available as a weekly PDF or as RDF/XML. Details are at <http://www.bl.uk/bibliographic/natbibweekly.html>

8. The BNB records are available as Linked Open Data. The Linked Open BNB includes published and forthcoming books as well as

serial publications. Details are at
<http://www.bl.uk/bibliographic/datafree.html>

DRAWBACK

- It is not available on CD-ROM.
- No printed list available as it stopped in December 2011.

CONCLUSION

The BNB is the single most comprehensive listing of UK titles. It is an important national resource that has the potential to be used as a key for knowledge development. In co-operation with other organisations, Collection Metadata is currently developing plans for further extending the scope and coverage of the national bibliography.

REFERENCES

- <http://www.bl.uk/bibliographic/natbib.html>
- <https://www.ifla.org/node/2217>
- <http://bnb.bl.uk>
- http://search.bl.uk/primo_library/libweb/action/search.do?vid=BLBNB

- https://www.bl.uk/bibliographic/pdfs/bnb_60th_birthday.pdf

ASSIGNMENT
ON
BRITISH NATIONAL
BIBLIOGRAPHY

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